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Evaluating the fumigant, insecticidal, and attractive properties of
monoterpenes and phenylpropenes, on *Bactrocera zonata* (Diptera:
Tephritidae)

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Abstract

The regular application of synthetic insecticides causes harm to humans and the environment and has initiated thorough research into safe and effective alternatives for insect control. Due to these damages, monoterpenes and phenylpropenes are attractive as pesticides for producing insecticides that are completely biodegradable, safe, and efficient. These substances are toxic at high concentrations and can either attract or repel insects at reduced levels due to their high volatility. The peach fruit fly, *Bactrocera zonata* (Saunders) (Diptera: Tephritidae), attacks fruits and vegetables such as mango, peach, fig, guava, citrus, apple, and tomato, also causing economic harm. Studied five monoterpenes [P-Cymene (99%), \pm Citronellal (95%), Carvone (98%), $\text{\textcircled{R}}$ Fenchone (98%), and Cuminaldehyde, (98%)] and one phenylpropene (trans-cinnamaldehyde (99%)] for fumigant toxicity to adults of *B. zonata*. The exposure time increased the toxicity of compounds by increasing the compounds' concentration. The studies made it clearer that the most hazardous substances to adult *B. zonata* are after 48, 72, and 96 hrs. were Cuminaldehyde, which was significantly the most potent compound ($LC_{50} = 56.92, 46.11, \text{ and } 15.97 \text{ mg/liter air, respectively}$). The peach fruit flies *B. zonata* were more attracted to P-Cymene (99%) and \pm Citronellal (95%) at concentrations (25, 50, and 100 mg/L) than the other monoterpenes. Attraction in adults increased with increased time of exposure and slightly increased when attracted by increasing concentration to 50 mg/L. Nevertheless, with increased concentration to 100 mg/L, five of the monoterpenes become repellent to the adults of *B. zonata*; additionally, phenylpropene trans-cinnamaldehyde (99%) was repellent at different concentrations. Generally, the attraction relatively diminishes with increasing concentration; it becomes an insect repellent. P-Cymene and \pm Citronellal both dramatically decreased the fecundity and fertility of adult *B. zonata* at concentrations of 2.5 and 5 mg/L.

Introduction

Fruit flies (Diptera: Tephritidae) are common along the tropics and subtropics of the globe and cause significant economic damage to fruit and vegetable crops (Chinajariyawong *et al.*, 2003). There are around 5,000 species and 500 genera in the Tephritidae family that are known to exist globally (Papadopoulos *et al.*, 2024). Tephritid flies, which attack fruits and vegetables, are the most common cause of economic damage globally (Rasool *et al.*, 2023).

Some species in the genus *Bactrocera* are polyphagous, known for their high reproductive ratio and dispersive capacity. Peach fruit fly (PFF), *Bactrocera zonata* (Saunders) (Diptera: Tephritidae), documented for the first time in Egypt by Efflatoun (1924) in Port Said. After going missing for a few decades, it was found again in a guava orchard in Alexandria's El-Agamy area (El-Minshawy *et al.*, 1999).

Peach fruit fly (PFF), *B. zonata* (Saunders), is one of the most serious polyphagous insect pests (Fletcher, 1987). It attacks a large host range of fruit and vegetable hosts, such as mango, peach, fig, guava, citrus, tomato, and apple (Kapoor and Agarwall, 1982 and White and Elson-Harris, 1994). Rasool (2025) discovered that *B. zonata* may modify its host preferences depending on the availability of host plants, with apricot (*Prunus armeniaca*) being the most favored fruit and jujube (*Ziziphus jujuba*) being the least. When it came to vegetables, *B. zonata* preferred bitter melon (*Momordica charantia*) and pumpkin (*Cucurbita pepo*). Female fruit flies choose their hosts according to various key traits of fruit plants, such as color, size, shape, and scent (Mahfuza *et al.*, 2011). This attraction is facilitated by an insect's scent receptors, specifically the antennae and the maxillary palp (Biasazin, 2017).

Synthetic pesticides are currently the mainstay of field insect pest management techniques. However, the adverse effects for human health and the environment are associated with the frequent use of synthetic insecticides, which has sparked extensive study into safe and efficient insect management alternatives. Numerous potential substitutes, including microorganisms, natural enemies (Parasitoids and predators), and botanical pesticides (Neem oil, azadirachtin, pyrethrum, vegetable oils, and essential oils), have been researched and applied to the management of insect pests. Plant-incorporated protectants and biochemical insecticides (repellents, attractants, and antifeedants) (Abdelgaleil *et al.*, 2023). One of the fractions of aromatic plants most frequently used for industrial applications and which has shown promise for use in IPM is the fraction of volatile fragrant compounds commonly called "essential oils" (Regnault-Roger, 1997). The major constituents of the plant essential oils belonging to the terpenes are monoterpenes, phenylpropenes, and sesquiterpenes.

Effective biological pesticides are plant essential oils and their bioactive components, such as monoterpenes, phenylpropenes, and sesquiterpenes (Zhou and Jander, 2021). These components have been shown to demonstrate various biological effects on certain economically significant insect pests, as they can function as insecticides (Abdelgaleil *et al.*, 2009 and Saad *et al.*, 2018). A prefix that indicates the minimum number of terpene units needed for assembly is used to classify terpenes according to the number of isoprene units in the molecule (Ninkuu *et al.*, 2021). Hemiterpenes, sesquiterpenes, diterpenes, sesterterpenes, triterpenes, sesquarterpenes, tetraterpenes, polyterpenes, norisoprenoids, and

monoterpenes are the main categories of terpenes.

Monoterpenes, which have the chemical formula $C_{10}H_{16}$, are a type of terpenes made up of two isoprene units (Wink, 2006). Contain different functional groups that make them classified as alcohols, aldehydes, ketones, or esters (Bakkali *et al.*, 2008). Phenylpropenes constitute an important group of aromatic plant substances, defined by a benzene ring attached to a propenyl side chain (C_6-C_3 framework). Several of these phenylpropenes, frequently found in essential oils, are classified as either phenols or phenol ethers (Atkinson, 2018). A class of molecules with 15 carbons is known as sesquiterpenes (Modzelewska *et al.*, 2005).

A common trend in various areas globally is the substitution of insecticides with substances and eco-friendly and sustainable pesticides with synthetic spraying methods. One of the interesting alternatives is the use of natural plant extracts, which are recognized for being less harmful to non-target species, the ecosystem, and human health (Gab Alla *et al.*, 2025). Numerous biological actions for monoterpenes and phenylpropenes, including fungicidal, insecticidal, antifeedant, antibacterial, and herbicidal effects on agricultural pests, have been demonstrated. Monoterpenes and phenylpropenes are appealing as pesticides and precursor chemicals for the creation of insecticides that are totally biodegradable, safe, and effective (Sharma *et al.*, 2013; Ahuja *et al.*, 2015 and Saad *et al.*, 2018). and became insecticides that break down naturally (Salakhutdinov *et al.*, 2017).

Essential oils can be toxic, repellent, or attractive depending on the dosage (Bedini *et al.*, 2019). In general, essential oils are toxic at their greatest concentration and either attract or repel insects at lower concentrations.

Monoterpenes, which are the main components of essential oils, are found in many different plants. Because of their highly volatile and distinctive fragrances, they are the cause of many plants' particular aromas and odors. (Abdelgaleil *et al.*, 2019). They account for almost 90% of the oil makeup in some aromatic plants (De Sousa, 2011). And play a role in various ecological functions in plants, including attracting pollinators, allelopathy, and defense against microbial diseases and herbivores (Langenheim, 1994 and Schewe *et al.*, 2011).

Recorded monoterpenes (Such as eucalyptol, borneol, camphor, bornyl acetate, carvacrol, (-)-menthol, γ -terpinene, (+)- α -pinene, (-)- β -pinene, and P-Cymene) are the key components of essential oils obtained via liquid extraction and steam distillation from edible and therapeutic plants (Crozier *et al.*, 2006). Special, P-Cymene [1-methyl-4-(1-methylethyl)-benzene] is an alkyl-substituted aromatic hydrocarbon present in nature, whose benzene ring advantages the substitution of a methyl and an isopropyl group and which is considered to be the most important monoterpene compound occurring in aromatic plants, such as thyme and oregano. P-Cymene is found in more than 100 plant species, including many belonging to the Thymus, Origanum, Ocimum (Lamiaceae), Eucalyptus (Mirtaceae), Protium (Burseraceae), and Artemisia (Asteraceae) genera (Phillis, 2005).

In Egypt thorough use of traditional insecticides has increased resistance development, unstable ecological systems, and harmful effects on public health. This stimulates the development of safer and eco-friendly tactics for insect control. Plant extracts and essential oils are among the most frequently used elements in modern integrated pest management strategies.

In light of this, the European Union unveiled plans to raise organic production by 25% and decrease the use of synthetic pesticides by 50% by 2030 as part of the European Biodiversity Strategy (Biodiversity Strategy for 2030).

The present paper discusses the different biological activities, such as insecticidal, attractant, and repellent effects of monoterpenes and one phenylpropene, as well as the ability of monoterpenes to affect mortality and some biological aspects of *B. zonata* adults.

Materials and methods

1. Insect culture and monoterpenes:

Adult of peach fruit fly *B. zonata* (Male and female) laboratory samples were received from the Plant Protection

Research Institute (PPRI), Department of Pests Horticultural Crops Research, Agricultural Research Center (ARC), Giza, Egypt, were placed in a plastic container with adult media, hydrolyzed protein, and granules of sugar (1:3) and water.

Five monoterpenes [P-Cymene (99%), \pm Citronellol (95%), Carvone (98%), \otimes Fenchone (98%), and Cuminaldehyde (98%)] and one phenylpropene [trans-cinnamaldehyde (99%)] are products of Sigma-Aldrich Chemical Co. (Germany). These monoterpenes fall into functional groups: Benzene, hydroxyl, primary alcohol, ketone, and aldehyde. Figure (1) shows the chemical structures of the monoterpenes and phenylpropenes tested that were investigated.

Figure (1): The molecular structures and the names of the tested monoterpenes and phenylpropenes.

2. Bioassay for fumigant activity:

The fumigant toxicity of monoterpenes and phenylpropene against adult *B. zonata* was assessed through a fumigant toxicity test (Scharf *et al.*, 2006). One liter glass containers were worked as a fumigation room. Various concentrations of compounds (25, 50, and 100 mg/L air) were injected onto filter paper (2 \times 3 cm) that was

affixed to the bottoms of jars. The container that held twenty flies was enclosed with its jar lid. Control jars using filter paper that contains acetone. The number of dead insects and percentages of mortality were recorded. The lethal concentration (LC₅₀) and probit analysis were calculated after a 48, 72, and 96-hour exposure period.

3. Attractiveness tests:

A simple olfactometer (Pow *et al.*, 1999) was used in lab studies to measure the attraction of examined monoterpenes and phenylpropenes to adult *B. zonata* at different concentrations. The plastic container (9 cm x 18 cm x 23 cm) containing seven arms (Five monoterpenes and one phenylpropene + one control) is connected with a cylindrical plastic container. A cylindrical plastic container (8 cm x 16 cm) connected with a plastic container that contains insects by arms half a meter tall. The external surfaces of the seven cylindrical plastic and plastic containers were covered. A hundred adults (Approximately one male for every female), 3-5 days old, were placed in a plastic container with adult media, hydrolyzed yeast, and granules of sugar (1:3) and water (Khan *et al.*, 2016). While the tested attractant compounds were placed in the seven cylindrical plastic containers. The concentrations of monoterpenes and phenylpropenes (25, 50, and 100 mg/L) were put on filter paper and placed in cylindrical plastic containers. The numbers of attracted adults were recorded after 12, 24, 48, 72, and 96 hrs. The experiment was carried out under laboratory conditions of $25 \pm 2.2^\circ\text{C}$ and RH. $74 \pm 9\%$ with repetition three times.

4. The direct exposition and biological measurements:

The achieved monoterpenes and phenylpropene with the best attraction activity were chosen to examine their biological activity measurements against adults of the peach fruit fly *B. zonata*, as mentioned by Ouarhach *et al.* (2022). Shortened, twenty adults of *B. zonata* (females and males), both newly emerged (1-2 days old), were included in a cage (25 cm x 25 cm) with a standard diet composed of hydrolyzed yeast and granules of sugar (1:3), along with 2 ml of P-Cymene (99%) and \pm Citronellal (95%) solved in 90%

ethanol to reach final concentrations of 2.5 and 5 mg/L. The adult was given water with a wet cotton after the solvent evaporated. The newly emerging adults are put in the plastic cage with treatment. A control procedure was using distilled water and 90% ethanol. The adults were staying at $25 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$, 70% relative humidity, and a 12:12 h photoperiod. The number of fly mortality was followed every day for 96 hrs., the pre-ovipositional period, ovipositional period, number of laid eggs/females, and percentage of hatched eggs were recorded.

4. Statistical analysis:

Lethal concentration (LC_{50}) was determined using LdpLine software, which was employed to conduct probit analysis of concentration-mortality data following Finney (1971). Additionally, data obtained in this experiment were evaluated using analysis of variance (ANOVA) succeeded by least notable distinction (LSD). A probability of 0.05 or lower was less significant. Every examination was performed utilizing Costat (Version: 6.303). All data are shown as averages \pm standard deviation (SD), and every experiment was conducted three times.

Results and discussion

1. The fumigant toxicities of monoterpenes and phenylpropene to adult *Bactrocera zonata*:

The fumigant toxicities of monoterpenes and phenylpropene to adult *B. zonata*, in Table (1) shows the probit analysis results for bioassays on *B. zonata* demonstrated significant effectiveness in killing insects. The exposure time increased the toxicity of compounds by increasing the compounds' concentration and exposure time. Showed most hazardous substances to adult *B. zonata* after 48, 72, and 96 hrs. was Cuminaldehyde, the most potent compound ($\text{LC}_{50} = 56.92, 46.11, \text{ and } 15.97 \text{ mg/liter air, respectively}$). While Cuminaldehyde

comes next in toxicity after 48 hrs. ⓂFenchone, Carvone, trans-cinnamaldehyde, P-Cymene, and ±Citronellal were ($LC_{50} = 132.40, 158.05, 184.55, 200.0, \text{ and } 264.98$ mg/liter air, respectively). While comes next Cuminaldehyde after 72 hrs. Carvone, trans-cinnamaldehyde, ⓂFenchone, ±Citronellal, and P-Cymene were ($LC_{50} = 70.0, 77.1, 92.85, 101.97, \text{ and } 188.54$ mg/liter air, respectively). Finally, following Cuminaldehyde in toxicity after 96 hrs. were trans-cinnamaldehyde, Carvone, ⓂFenchone, ±Citronellal and P-Cymene ($LC_{50} = 30.80, 37.09, 39.64, 41.17, \text{ and } 89.46$ mg/liter air, respectively). Showed comparatively fewer toxicities against adult *B. zonata* ± Citronellal and P-Cymene. The confidence limits of Cuminaldehyde did not overlap with LC_{50} values of trans-cinnamaldehyde.

Nevertheless, the results indicated above agree with the findings of other researchers regarding various fruit flies and monoterpenes. Gab Alla *et al.* (2025) describe the highest toxicity to *Ceratitis capitata* (Wiedemann) (Diptera: Tephritidae), as evidenced after 48 hrs. were Cuminaldehyde and geraniol. Demonstrate De Souza *et al.* (2024) that the terpenes carvacrol and L-(-)-Carvone and the phenylpropanoids (E)-cinnamaldehyde and (E)-anethole presented extreme toxicities to the cherry vinegar fly *D. suzukii* adults. Certain monoterpenes, including (±)-Citronellal and (+)-Pulegone, show significant toxicity to fruit flies and may serve as biopesticides. Monoterpenes like eugenol, thymol, and carvacrol, which are present in essential oils, also exhibit strong fumigant toxicity and could be used as natural pesticides to control fruit flies (Zhang *et al.*, 2016). In addition to the effect of monoterpenes on types of fruit flies, it had an effect on other species as the recorded

antifeedant of the melaleuca weevil *Oxyops vitiosa* (Pascoe) (Coleoptera: Curculionidae) (Wheeler *et al.*, 2002). Additionally, Huang and Ho (1998) recorded that the fumigant toxicity of cinnamaldehyde was higher for the red flour beetle *Tribolium castaneum* (Herbst) (Coleoptera: Tenebrionidae) than for the maize weevil *Sitophilus zeamais* Motschulsky (Coleoptera: Curculionidae)

The toxicity of monoterpenes is greatly influenced by their functional group; in general, oxygenated monoterpenes (Alcohols, ketones, and aldehydes) have higher, though variable, toxicity than hydrocarbon monoterpenes. While monoterpene hydrocarbons frequently have a stronger effect on particular insect pests, oxygenated molecules such as 4-terpineol and P-Cymene have considerable inhibitory effects (Anaerobic digestion) (Zhang *et al.*, 2016 and Kordali *et al.*, 2007). According to Abdelgaleil (2010), oxygenated monoterpenes were more harmful to third-instar larvae of the cotton leafworm *S. littoralis* than monoterpene hydrocarbons. Rice and Coats (1994) discovered that some monoterpene ketones were more effective toxins than monoterpene alcohols. The effect of toxic monoterpenes on insects is not completely clarified. Nonetheless, it has been noted that monoterpenes demonstrated inhibitory impacts on acetylcholine esterases (AChEs). Ryan and Byrne (1988) and Abdelgaleil *et al.* (2009) observed that monoterpenes can discourage (AChEs) in insects and various other organisms. Moreover, it has been mentioned that monoterpenes and phenylpropanoids serve as natural insecticides and repellents derived from plants, primarily by affecting the nervous systems of insects. They trigger neurotoxic effects, function as fumigants leading to respiratory

distress, inhibit enzymes such as acetylcholinesterase (AChE), and influence receptors like GABA and tyramine receptors. Additionally, they

inflict physical harm to tissues, interfering with metabolic processes (Qasim *et al.*, 2024).

Table (1): Fumigant toxicity of monoterpenes and phenylpropenes against the adults of *Bactrocera zonata* after 24, 48, 72 and 96 hrs. of exposure.

Compounds	Time	LC50 ^a mg/liters (Confidence limits)	Slope ±SE ^b	X ² ^c	P ^d
P-Cymene (99%)	48 hrs.	200.0 (117.88-1118.55)	1.16±0.33	0.05	0.81
	72 hrs.	188.54 (111.72-1059.07)	1.12±0.33	0.06	0.80
	96 hrs.	89.46 (71.30-131.34)	1.72±0.32	3.0	0.08
±Citronellal (95%)	48 hrs.	264.98 (145.31-1834.47)	1.28±0.36	0.12	0.73
	72 hrs.	101.97 (79.74-130.66)	2.20±0.13	2.0	0.85
	96 hrs.	41.17 (35.17-47.26)	2.56±0.33	1.53	0.22
Carvone (98%)	48 hrs.	158.05 (115.13-300.86)	2.0±0.38	3.68	0.06
	72 hrs.	70.0 (59.93-87.21)	2.20±0.33	2.63	0.11
	96 hrs.	37.09 (32.28-41.79)	3.12±0.36	0.53	0.47
®Fenchone (98%)	48 hrs.	132.40 (98.85-237.07)	1.80±0.35	0.04	0.83
	72 hrs.	92.85 (71.28-153.61)	1.47±0.31	0.94	0.33
	96 hrs.	39.64 (32.12-46.97)	2.02±0.32	0.24	0.63
Cuminaldehyde (98%)	48 hrs.	56.92 (48.78-67.57)	2.25±0.32	1.58	0.21
	72 hrs.	46.11 (37.49-55.75)	1.83±0.31	3.58	0.06
	96 hrs.	15.97 (7.60-22.55)	1.72±0.36	0.01	0.91
Trans-cinnamaldehyde (99%)	48 hrs.	184.55 (110.84-942.26)	1.14±0.33	2.73	0.09
	72 hrs.	77.1 (56.44-149.54)	1.08±0.30	2.57	0.11
	96 hrs.	30.80 (22.13-37.99)	1.76±0.32	3.52	0.06

^a The concentration causing 50% mortality

^b Slope of the concentration-mortality regression line ± standard error

^c Chi-squared value

^d Probability value

2. Performance of *Bactrocera zonata* adults to attractants:

The reactions of the adults of the peach fruit fly *B. zonata* in the simple olfactometer for concentrations of 25 mg/L of the five monoterpenes (P-Cymene (99%), ±Citronellal (95%), Carvone (98%), ®Fenchone (98%), and Cuminaldehyde (98%)) and one phenylpropene trans-cinnamaldehyde (99%) were tested and are shown in Table (2). The general means were at a 25 mg/L concentration and were 22.13, 10.47, 3.13, 5.7, 2.93, and 1.87, respectively, in comparison to the control (0.33). The peach fruit flies *B. zonata* were more attracted to P-Cymene (99%) and ±Citronellal (95%) than the other monoterpenes, whereas the phenylpropene Trans-

cinnamaldehyde (99%) attracted the fewest insects. Statistical analyses indicated that the second day found no significant difference between Carvone (98%), ®Fenchone (98%), and Cuminaldehyde (98%). P-Cymene (99%) and ±Citronellal (95%) had a significantly higher attraction for adult *B. zonata* on the third and fourth days. Additional Fenchone (98%) significantly weakened the response until the third day but rose in attraction on the fourth day.

The response of the adults of *B. zonata* to a 50 mg/L concentration of the five monoterpenes (P-Cymene (99%), ±Citronellal (95%), Carvone (98%), ®Fenchone (98%), and Cuminaldehyde (98%)) and one phenylpropene, trans-cinnamaldehyde

(99%), was tested and is shown in Table (3). General means were 22.33, 15.0, 12.5, 8.9, 7.7, and 0.73, respectively. On the first day, there was no significant difference between P-Cymene (99%), \pm Citronellal (95%), and Carvone (98%) in attracting adults. On the second day, there was no significant difference between Carvone (98%) and \pm Citronellal (95%) in attracting flies. It was non-significant between \oplus Fenchone (98%) and Cuminaldehyde (98%) on the second and third days. Statistical analyses indicated that P-Cymene (99%) and \pm Citronellal (95%) had a significantly higher attraction among adults on the third and fourth days. While appearing, trans-cinnamaldehyde (99%) significantly

lowers the attraction of adults throughout the experience. Attraction in adults increased with increased time of exposure and slightly increased when attracted by increasing concentration to 50 mg/L. Nevertheless, P-Cymene (99%) and \pm Citronellal (95%) remain the most attractive. However, the results mentioned agree with various researchers' discoveries regarding different monoterpenes and insect species. Some monoterpenes can attract fruit flies, so they can be used to lure them into traps. Niogret and Epsky (2018) reported that Linalool alone attracted the same percentage of *C. capitata* flies and confirmed that this chemical was mainly responsible for attracting them in ginger root oil.

Table (2): Attraction of *Bactrocera zonata* adults to monoterpenes and phenylpropene at 25 (mg/L) conc. after 12, 24, 48, 72, and 96 hrs. under laboratory conditions.

Compounds	Mean number of flies Attracted / hour \pm SD					GM
	12 hrs.	24 hrs.	48 hrs.	72 hrs.	96 hrs.	
P-Cymene (99%)	9.0 \pm 0.8a	16.33 \pm 0.5a	23.33 \pm 0.5a	28.0 \pm 1.6a	34.0 \pm 0.0a	22.13
\pmCitronellal (95%)	1.67 \pm 0.5bc	3.0 \pm 0.0b	6.0 \pm 0.8b	16.0 \pm 0.5b	25.66 \pm 0.5b	10.47
Carvone (98%)	1 \pm 0.82bcd	2.0 \pm 0.8bc	3.33 \pm 0.4c	4.33 \pm 0.5c	5.0 \pm 0.8d	3.13
\oplusFenchone (98%)	1.0 \pm 0.0bcd	2.33 \pm 0.5bc	2.33 \pm 0.5cd	3.33 \pm 0.5c	20.0 \pm 0.8c	5.7
Cuminaldehyde (98%)	2.0 \pm 0.8b	2.33 \pm 0.5bc	2.33 \pm 0.5cd	3.33 \pm 1.2c	4.66 \pm 0.5de	2.93
Trans-cinnamaldehyde (99%)	0.67 \pm 0.5cd	1.67 \pm 0.5c	1.67 \pm 0.5d	2.0 \pm 0.8c	3.33 \pm 1.0e	1.87
Control	0.33 \pm 0.5d	0.33 \pm 0.5d	0.33 \pm 0.5e	0.33 \pm 0.5c	0.33 \pm 0.5f	0.33
LSD (0.05)	1.32	1.08	1.14	6.2	1.5	-

Means followed by the same letter in column are not significantly different according to the L.S.D. test at the 0.05 probability level. GM= General mean.

Table (3): Attraction of *Bactrocera zonata* adults to monoterpenes and phenylpropene at 50(mg/L) conc. after 12, 24, 48, 72, and 96 hrs. under laboratory conditions.

Compounds	Mean number of flies attracted / hour \pm SD					GM
	12 hrs.	24 hrs.	48 hrs.	72 hrs.	96 hrs.	
P-Cymene (99%)	7.0 \pm 0.8a	11.33 \pm 1.2a	25.0 \pm 0.0a	31.0 \pm 0.8a	37.33 \pm 1.0a	22.33
\pmCitronellal (95%)	1.67 \pm 0 c	10.0 \pm 0.8a	13.0 \pm 1.6b	22.33 \pm 2.1b	28.0 \pm 2.2b	15.0
Carvone (98%)	7.0 \pm 0.8a	10 \pm 0.8a	13.33 \pm 1.2b	15.0 \pm 0.8c	15.33 \pm 0.5d	12.5
\oplusFenchone (98%)	2.33 \pm 0.5c	6.33 \pm 0.5b	8.33 \pm 0.5c	9.0 \pm 0.0d	18.33 \pm 1.2cd	8.9
Cuminaldehyde (98%)	4.33 \pm 0.5b	8.0 \pm 0.8b	8.0 \pm 0.8c	9.33 \pm 0.5d	9.0 \pm 0.8e	7.7
Trans - cinnamaldehyde (99%)	0.0 \pm 0.0d	0.67 \pm 0.5c	1.0 \pm 0.0d	1.0 \pm 0.0e	1.0 \pm 0.0f	0.73
Control	0.0 \pm 0.0d	0.33 \pm 0.5c	0.66 \pm 0.5d	1.0 \pm 0.0e	1.0 \pm 0.0f	0.07
LSD (0.05)	2.05	2.75	3.15	3.73	5.30	-

Means followed by the same letter in column are not significantly different according to the L.S.D. test at the 0.05 probability level. GM= General mean.

The reply of the adults of *B. zonata* with increased concentration to 100 mg/L reduced attraction to the five monoterpenes (P-Cymene (99%), \pm Citronellal (95%), Carvone (98%), \oplus Fenchone (98%), and Cuminaldehyde (98%)) and one phenylpropene trans-cinnamaldehyde (99%) was tested and is shown in Table (4). General means were 9.6, 8.9, 7.5, 4.7, 3.9, and 0.7, respectively, compared with the control (0.13). Statistical analyses show \pm Citronellal (95%) was highly significant till the second day, while P-Cymene (99%) was a higher significant attraction for adults on the third and fourth days. Although Carvone (98%) was significantly higher than \oplus Fenchone (98%) and cuminaldehyde (98%) until the third day, it was non-significant between Carvone (98%) and \oplus Fenchone (98%) on the fourth day. While Trans-cinnamaldehyde (99%) was less attractive to adults, it was a strong repellent to *B. zonata* at every concentration. This result agrees with Yursida *et al.* (2025), who mentioned that the primary ingredient in cinnamon oil, trans-cinnamaldehyde, and functions as a strong natural insecticide, acaricide, and repellent against a variety of insects, such as ants, mosquitoes, and houseflies. Trans-cinnamaldehyde had a strong repellent effect against adult female yellow fever mosquito *Aedes aegypti* (L.) (Diptera : Culicidae) when sprayed (Kamari *et al.*, 2022).

Generally, the monoterpenes' attraction relatively diminishes by increasing concentration; it becomes an insect repellent. These results mentioned earlier align with the discoveries made by various

researchers regarding different monoterpenes and insect species. Tian *et al.* (2024) reported that the Asian tiger mosquito *Aedes albopictus* (Skuse) was attracted to Citronellal, linalool, citral, and geraniol at lower concentrations and repelled at greater quantities. Qasim *et al.* (2024) mentioned that monoterpenes are naturally used as pesticides and herbicides since they repel insects and stunt plant growth. Alternatively, the repelling properties of monoterpenes, abundant in aromatic plants like lavender and mint, can deter fruit flies from certain locations (Sfara *et al.*, 2009).

At low concentrations, monoterpenes are for pollination or herbivory signaling, but at larger quantities, they can be strong repellents or poisons. Often outperforming synthetic repellents like DEET, important repellent monoterpenes include limonene, thymol, carvacrol, and alpha-terpinene (Choi *et al.*, 2002 and Qasim *et al.*, 2024). This idea becomes clear in the Colorado potato beetle *Leptinotarsa decemlineata* Say (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae) and yellow mealworm *Tenebrio molitor* L.(Coleoptera: Tenebrionidae), which were repelled by compounds made from cinnamon (Taghizadeh Saroukola *et al.*, 2014; Wang *et al.*, 2015 and Martínez *et al.*, 2018). Recorded Qasim *et al.* (2024) and Chiu *et al.* (2017) that monoterpenes with high toxicity, including oxygenated substances like ketones, aldehydes, and epoxides, greatly reduce insect attraction by functioning as strong repellents, fumigants, and deterrents to feeding.

Table (4): Attraction of *Bactrocera zonata* adults to monoterpenes and phenylpropene at 100 (mg/L) conc. after 12, 24, 48, 72, and 96 hrs. under laboratory conditions.

Compounds	Mean number of flies attracted / hour \pm SD					GM
	12 hrs.	24 hrs.	48 hrs.	72 hrs.	96 hrs.	
P-Cymene (99%)	3.0 \pm 0.8b	5.0 \pm 0.8b	7.0 \pm 0.8b	14.33 \pm 1.2a	18.67 \pm 1.2a	9.6
\pm Citronellal (95%)	5.67 \pm 0.5a	7.33 \pm 0.5a	10.0 \pm 0.8a	10.33 \pm 1.2b	11.33 \pm 1.2b	8.9
Carvone (98%)	2.67 \pm 0.5b	6.0 \pm 0.8b	8.0 \pm 0.8b	10.0 \pm 0.8b	11.0 \pm 0.8b	7.5
α Fenchone (98%)	1.0 \pm 0.0c	2.33 \pm 0.5c	4.0 \pm 0.8c	6.0 \pm 0.8c	10.33 \pm 1.2b	4.7
Cuminaldehyde (98%)	1.0 \pm 0.0c	1.33 \pm 0.5c	4.0 \pm 0.8c	6.0 \pm 0.8c	7.0 \pm 0.0c	3.9
Trans-cinnamaldehyde (99%)	0.0 \pm 0.0d	0.0 \pm 0.0d	1.0 \pm 0.0d	1.0 \pm 0.0d	1.66 \pm 1.0d	0.7
Control	0.0 \pm 0.0d	0.0 \pm 0.0d	0.0 \pm 0.0d	0.33 \pm 0.5d	0.33 \pm 0.5d	0.13
LSD (0.05)	0.85	1.15	1.48	1.87	2.06	-

Means followed by the same letter in column are not significantly different according to the L.S.D. test at the 0.05 probability level. GM= General mean.

The effect of different concentrations, 2.5 and 5 mg/L, of P-Cymene and \pm Citronellal on mortality and developmental parameters, such as adult mortality after 96 h, pre-ovipositional period, ovipositional period, no. laid eggs/female, and % hatched eggs of *B. zonata* adults, is shown in Table (5). The results detection that \pm Citronellal was significantly highly toxic to the adult after 4 days of treatment, particularly at the higher concentrations of 5 mg/L, was 26.67%. While mortality was 23.33% for P-Cymene after 96 hrs. at the same concentration. No significant difference between P-Cymene and \pm Citronellal at a concentration of 2.5 mg/L. These findings suggested that P-Cymene and \pm Citronellal had concentration-dependent effects on mortality. This finding validates the well-known theory that monoterpene concentration affects how effective they are as insecticides. While, P-Cymene and \pm Citronellal significantly extended the pre-ovipositional period at 5 mg/L (25.33 and 28.0 days, respectively) in comparison with the control (6.87 days). On the other hand, Citronellal decreased the period of oviposition (6.16 days) more than P-Cymene (10.23 days) at a concentration of 5 mg/L, and it was not significantly different from them at the concentration of 2.5 mg/L, the comparison with the control was

37.67 days. P-Cymene and \pm Citronellal both dramatically decreased adult fecundity at 2.5 and 5 mg/L compared to the control group (105.2 eggs/female), P-Cymene and Citronellal treatments significantly reduced the quantity of eggs deposited per female at both concentrations. Also, the percentage of eggs that hatch, or fertility, is an effective indicator of an insect's ability for reproduction. At concentrations of 5 mg/L the percentage of eggs hatched was 23.32% in the P-Cymene treatment and decreased to 18.25% in the \pm Citronellal treatment. P-Cymene and \pm Citronellal reduced fertility at both concentrations non-significantly between them compared to the decreased fertility of adult *B. zonata* compared with 75.26% of the eggs hatched in the control treatments. Declining fertility is a sign of increased sterility. In accordance with these results, according to these findings, El-Minshawy *et al.* (2018) found that *B. zonata* oviposition was completely inhibited by the monoterpenes (Camphor, carvone, and menthol) at varying doses. Also, Siddiqi *et al.* (2006 and 2011) and Ur-Rehman *et al.* (2009) mentioned that plant extracts have been shown to prevent *B. zonata* oviposition. Further, Abdelgaleil *et al.* (2022) stated that treatment with (-)-Carvone, (-)-Citronellal, eugenol, p-cymene, and α -

pinene decreased pupal weight, decreased pupation percentage, and extended pupal time in comparison to control in *Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisduval) (Lepidoptera : Noctuidae) and recorded that (-)-Citronellal had the greatest effect on decreasing oviposition and egg hatching. Additionally, the influence of monoterpenes in other insects when the egg-laying behavior of the brown dog tick, *Rhipicephalus sanguineus*

(Latreille) (Acari: Ixodidae) was found, the monoterpene thymol generated degradation indications and interfered with oocytes' development (Matos *et al.*, 2014). According to Stamopoulos *et al.* (2007) monoterpenes (terpinen-4-ol, 1,8-cineole, linalool, R-(+)-limonene, and geraniol) reduced the fertility and egg hatchability of the confused flour beetle *Tribolium confusum* (Jacquelin du Val) (Coleoptera: Tenebrionidae).

Table (5): Impact of varying monoterpene concentrations on mortality and some biological aspects of *Bactrocera zonata* adults.

Compounds	Conc mg/L	Mortality after 96 hrs. (% \pm SD)	Pre-ovipositional period (Days) \pm SD	Ovipositional period (Days) \pm SD	No. laid eggs / female \pm SD	%Hatched eggs \pm SD
\pm Citronellal (95%)	2.5	10.0 \pm 0.0 c	23.67 \pm 2.9 bc	10.53 \pm 0.5 b	11.17 \pm 4.9 b	27.94 \pm 7.7 b
	5.0	26.67 \pm 2.4 a	28.0 \pm 2.2 a	6.16 \pm 2.3 c	7.0 \pm 1.0 b	18.25 \pm 3.5 b
P-Cymene	2.5	10.0 \pm 0.0 c	19.67 \pm 2.1 c	12.73 \pm 0.7 b	11.83 \pm 1.7 b	27.58 \pm 6.8 b
	5.0	23.33 \pm 2.4 b	25.33 \pm 1.2 ab	10.23 \pm 0.2 b	10.17 \pm 2.5 b	23.32 \pm 2.5 b
Control	-	0.0 \pm 0.0 d	6.87 \pm 0.24 d	37.67 \pm 2.05 a	105.2 \pm 6.8 a	75.26 \pm 4.2 a
LSD (0.05)	-	3.32	4.31	3.22	8.99	11.82

Means followed by the same letter in column are not significantly different according to the L.S.D. test at the 0.05 probability level.

The investigation showed that studies of the monoterpene Cuminaldehyde (98%) showed the highest fumigant toxicity activity against adults of *B. zonata*. It was indicated that P-Cymene and \pm Citronellal were the most attractive and reduced fertility and fecundity of adult *B. zonata*. According to these findings. Therefore, monoterpenes are comparatively safe natural remedies for insect pest management and have no detrimental impacts on the environment or human health. Furthermore, no insect resistance has been found for these materials.

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